

**MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR STUDY OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES
WITH A VIEW TO TOUGHNESS CHARACTERIZATION**

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ABSTRACT

Defining methods for the toughness characterization of brittle matrix composites needs a good understanding of their mechanical behavior. With this aim, 2D-SiC/SiC composites have been tested under tension, compression and bending. The general features of the stress-strain curves and load-displacement curves lead to consider 2D-SiC/SiC as quasi elastic materials. A comparison between 2D-SiC/SiC and 2D-C/C composites allows to depict their mechanical behavior with a simple model based on the occurrence of friction phenomena between fibers and microcracked matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites (CMC) display quite interesting performances with respect to monolithic ceramics [1]. Properties such as rupture work, toughness, impact and thermal fatigue resistances have been widely improved due to:

1) the subdivision of the material: the fibrous morphology of one component and the small dimension of the fiber spacing,

2) the building up, within the heterogeneous material, of various energy dissipating mechanisms [2, 3].

Unfortunately, all these contributions which give CMC advantageous properties lead to many difficulties in material characterization. CMC have often been reported to exhibit imperfect non-linear elasticity and questionable "pseudo plastic" behavior with, as a result, a lack of reliability in the determination of elastic constants as well as rupture parameters.

For toughness evaluation, defining an intrinsic parameter as for monolithic brittle elastic materials has been subjected to extended methodological studies but remains uncertain. Drawing crack growth resistance curves seems to be necessary and can be performed according to different procedures. One way consists in taking into account the main apparent features of load-deformation or stress-strain curves, that is considering CMC as non-linear non-elastic materials. In this case, crack growth resistance curves are derived from load cycling, the dissipated energy related to compliance increase being distinguished from the non-elastic contribution corresponding to permanent deformation [4 - 6]. This kind of rather complex methods might depend on cycling conditions and cannot avoid the difficulties dealing with compliance determination. Otherwise, assuming CMC as linear elastic materials whose rigidity decreases as damaging mechanisms extend, allows an easy drawing of R-curves. However, such an assumption is contestable when CMC exhibit large permanent deformations.

The aim of the present study is to discuss the possibility to consider CMC as quasi elastic materials, from the examination and comparison of 2D-SiC/SiC and 2D-C/C composite mechanical behavior.

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF 2D-SiC/SiC COMPOSITES

Materials

2D-SiC/SiC composites have been processed by chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) of silicon carbide within preforms made of a stacking of SiC (Nicalon) fabric layers. The material densification is performed up to a residual porosity of about 10%. The resulting composites are orthotropic with two identical principal axes (1) and (2). Although the intrinsic mechanical characteristics of the CVI matrix are not well known, the following main remarks can be pointed out by comparing 2D-SiC/SiC and 2D-carbon/carbon composites:

1) when, on one hand, the carbon matrix stiffness is lower than that of the carbon fibers, on the other hand, the SiC (CVI) matrix rigidity is higher than that of the SiC fibers,

2) in both cases, the matrix rupture strain is lower than that of the fibers so that matrix cracking occurs prior to fiber fracture,

3) due to the fibrous structure of the initial 2D preforms, the composite mechanical performances along the (1) and (2) fiber directions are higher than those generally obtained for both type of composites in the direction (3) perpendicular to the

fabric layers. Thus, the study of the 2D-ceramic/ceramic behavior has been performed , at first, along the (1) or (2) directions.

Elasticity and pseudo-plasticity

The composites have been tested under static loading in tension, compression, three points and four points bending as well as under cyclic loading at various frequencies on bending notched specimens. A particular attention has been paid to the measurement of tensile and compressive deformations with an extensometer and to the determination of bending displacements taking into account the Brinelling effects related to load application. Acoustic emission has been used in order to correlate damaging events occurring within the composites and the main features of the stress-strain or load-displacement curves as illustrated in figure 1.

From the results of the testing, the following description of the 2D-SiC/SiC composite behavior can be given:

1) In tension, the first part of the stress-strain curve (i.e. up to a stress level of about 30-40 MPa) exhibits a noticeable rigidification effect (Fig. 1). However, this phenomenon is not supported by the other tests as illustrated in figures 2 -4. This feature has been related to a somewhat realignment of the fibers in the vicinity of pores or microcracks. It should explain that this phenomenon cannot be pointed out under compression loads. During bending tests the rigidification does not occur in the same parts of the specimen section as the load increases, so that, it is difficult to discern this effect even during four points bending.

2) The acoustic emission indicates the occurrence of damaging phenomena for tensile stresses above about 60 MPa which corresponds to a matrix strain of $250 \cdot 10^{-6}$. However, the damage remains moderate up to about 90-100 MPa since the composite stiffness is only slightly affected between 60 and 100 MPa.

3) It results from the previous remarks that the linear part of the stress-strain curves is rather limited. Once again, this feature is particularly significant during tensile tests for which microcracking phenomena take place within the whole specimen.

4) Above a stress of about 100 MPa which can be assumed as the yield stress σ_y (although the true yield stress corresponds in fact to the initiation of the damaging mechanisms) the composites are extensively damaged up to a rupture strain of about 0,20 - 0,25%. It gives the 2D-SiC/SiC composites a favorable " pseudo-plastic " behavior.

5) However, when loading the composites above σ_y , the extensive material damage does not lead to significant residual deformations after unloading whatever the testing procedure.

Figure 1. Tensile Stress-Strain curves for 2D-SiC/SiC composites.

Figure 2. Compression Stress-Strain curves for 2D-SiC/SiC composites.

Figure 3. Three points bending load-displacement curves for 2D-SiC/SiC composites.

Figure 4. Four points bending load-displacement curves for 2D-SiC/SiC composites.

6) Otherwise, load cycling reveals only small hysteresis loops which are particularly narrow during compression and bending tests. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that during each cycle the stress-strain curves related to loading and unloading intersect. This effect has been explained by complex sequences of fiber-matrix sliding and formation of impeding debris.

7) When the testing procedure enables the specimens to fail either by interlayer delamination or by intralayer failure, the composites tend to delaminate as shown during all the compression tests.

In summary, the mechanical behavior of 2D-SiC/SiC composites can be represented by two main domains particularly evidenced on the tensile stress-strain curves: (1) a slightly sigmoidal quasi-linear elastic part from which the composite elastic constants can be defined in the inflexion area of this first part of the curves, (2) a "pseudo-plastic" domain in which the composite is extensively damaged giving rise to more and more compliant materials as the matrix is progressively subdivided by microcracking. In this domain, the composite is better represented by quasi linear elastic materials with decreasing stiffness.

COMPARISON WITH THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF 2D-C/C COMPOSITES

2D-SiC/SiC composites have been compared to 2D carbon/carbon composites processed according to similar CVI methods. From the 2D-C/C mechanical characterization which has been detailed elsewhere, it comes out large similitudes in the general features of the stress-strain or load-displacement curves for both types of CMC, as illustrated in figure 5 [7]. So that, their elastic constants which have been derived from the same area of the stress-strain curves can be compared. Table 1 shows that the two types of composites belong to quite different ranges of stiffness due to the strong difference in the CVI matrix rigidity.

Regarding the various aspects which have been considered in the previous section, 2D-C/C composites differ from 2D-SiC/SiC CMC by the following main features:

1) The rigidification effect which also concerns the 2D-C/C composites during the first part of the loading spreads on a larger domain of the stress-strain curves.

2) The damaging mechanisms related to the matrix microcracking appears more progressively as shown by the absence of sudden activation of the acoustic emission.

3) As a result of the sigmoidal shape of the stress-strain curves, a quasi-linear elastic domain is difficult to distinguish from a "pseudo-plastic" domain.

4) When unloaded before failure 2D-C/C composites exhibit greater residual deformations particularly under compression and bending.

5) Furthermore, the hysteresis loops related to load cycling are larger and well shaped. But few activity of acoustic emission has been recorded during cycles.

6) A macroscopic examination of the failure surfaces tends to indicate that 2D-SiC/SiC are more brittle than 2D-C/C composites as shown by the rough surfaces mainly due to local delaminations of the carbon fabric layers. However, SEM examination reveals that fiber pull out phenomenon is more significant in 2D-SiC/SiC composites. Any way, a comparison concerning the failure brittleness is difficult since the levels of the rupture strengths and stored elastic energies are quite different.

It remains that 2D-C/C composites can also be regarded as a succession of quasi-elastic materials as damaging mechanisms extend. However, the small residual deformations and above all the significance of the hysteresis loops have to be explained. It is noteworthy that making use of various methods for toughness determination the specimen compliance must be measured at different steps of loading. For instance, a tangent at hysteresis loops may have to be chosen.

MODEL FOR CMC MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR

As illustrated in figure 7, a model has been proposed to represent the mechanical behavior of CMC whose matrix rupture strain is smaller than that of the fibers ($\epsilon_{m}^R < \epsilon_f^R$). This model deals with the coupling of elastic and friction elements and assumes the material behavior as independent of time (no viscous elements). Each part of the model is related to:

- 1) the zones of the composites in which fiber-matrix bonding is strong enough to allow equal deformations of both constituents,
- 2) the friction between some parts of fibers and matrix,
- 3) the fiber parts for which no friction occurs with the matrix.

On the basis of the previous model and assuming the fiber-matrix friction as defined by a load threshold (F_c during loading and F_d during unloading), the mechanical behavior of damaged composites can be represented by load cycles from initial unstressed states. Figure 7 shows some cases illustrating this representation with the following characteristic parameters:

$$\alpha = \frac{(Cm_2 + Cf_2)Fc}{Cf_2}$$

$$\beta = \frac{(Cm_2 + Cf_2)}{Cf_2} (F_c + F_d)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{Cf_2 (Cm_1 + Cf_1) Fc}{Cm_1 Cf_1 + (Cf_2 + Cf_3) (Cm_1 + Cf_1)}$$

$$\delta r = Cf_2 \cdot Fd$$

Each case can briefly be described as follows:

1) When the fiber-matrix friction is low, both the width of the hysteresis loop and the residual deformation are small. In this case, the composite is quasi linear elastic and the rate of damage can be characterized by the secant modulus since γ is very small (Fig. 7a),

2) when the fiber-matrix friction is very significant at one during loading and, in the same time, during unloading, the residual deformation is always large but the hysteresis loop can be either extended or small depending on β (Fig. 7b),

3) when the fiber-matrix friction exhibits a strong deviation between loading and un-loading due, for example, to difference in the matrix and fiber Poisson's ratio, the hysteresis loops are extended and residual deformations can be either large or negligible depending on F_d (Fig. 7c and d). In fact, residual deformations are directly related to fiber-matrix friction during unloading and to the fiber rigidity,

4) otherwise, the sequences corresponding to fiber-matrix sliding with or without friction, depending on their characteristics, can be more complex leading to partial hysteresis loops as illustrated in figure 7e. In such cases, the redistribution along the cycle, of the load between the fibers and the matrix can lead to changes in the friction characteristics giving rise to additional deformations and intersecting curves as illustrated in figure 7f.

Furthermore, the formation of debris can also modify slightly the curves rendering sometimes steeper the lower end of the loops and larger the residual deformations.

Figure 5. Tensile Stress-Strain curves for 2D-C/C composites.

TABLE 1
Elastic characteristics of 2D-SiC/SiC and 2D-C/C composites.

Material	2D SiC/SiC				2D C/C			
	Tension	Compre. sion	3 Pts bending	4 Pts bending	Tension	Compre. sion	3 Pts bending	4 Pts bending
E ₁ (GPa)	210-220	260-270	250	230	40-44	38-41	42	43
G ₁₂ (GPa)	-	-	15-17	-	-	-	4.0	-
G ₁₃ (GPa)	-	-	12-14	-	-	-	1.2	-
ν ₁₂	0.19	0.20	-	-	0.10	0.09	-	-
ν ₁₃	0.13	0.14-0.15	-	-	0.53	0.55	-	-

Figure 6. Schematic model representing the mechanical behavior of brittle matrix composites.

Figure 7. Schematic representation of load cycles for brittle matrix composites.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Many other cases could be derived from the model described above since the feature of the curves depends also on the composite constituent rigidities as shown by formula (1) - (4). However, this first approach correlated with the experimental comparison between 2D-C/C and 2D-SiC/SiC composites allows to explain their behavior as follows:

1) The main features of 2D-C/C composites (i.e., a small residual deformation and significant hysteresis loop) lead to consider their behavior as illustrated in figure 7d. The fiber-matrix friction is rather high during loading but the matrix rigidity is low compared to that of the fibers so that α and β are high ($C_f \ll C_m$) when γ is small and δr negligible. This kind of composites can be considered as elastic.

2) In addition to very small residual deformations, 2D-SiC/SiC composites exhibit narrow hysteresis loop, so that their behavior can be depicted by figure 7a, e or f. In any of these cases α , β , γ , δr are quite low due to reduced fiber-matrix friction and low matrix compliance compared to that of the fibers. 2D-SiC/SiC composites can be considered as quasi-linear elastic.

The two 2D-CMC which have been tested are quasi elastic materials whatever their state of damage. Thus, load-displacement curves related to notched specimens, as used for toughness evaluation, should not point out residual deformations. However, during unloading of notched specimens after crack growth, the compliance of the specimens may appear much smaller than it should be (it is sometimes smaller than the initial specimen compliance) due, for example, to formation of debris which impede crack closure. Therefore, notched specimens compliance derived from load cycling seems to be more uncertain than assuming the related CMC as linear elastic.

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